

COVID-19: A Systematic Review of Current Evidence and Key Knowledge Gaps

Catur Puspita Tyas Dayinta

Muhammadiyah University of Purwokerto

A. Introduction

a.1. Background

COVID-19 is an infectious disease caused by the SARS-CoV-2 virus, which emerged in late 2019 and rapidly spread around the world, causing a global pandemic. Understanding the virology, epidemiology, clinical features, and societal impacts of this novel coronavirus has been a major focus of the scientific community.

a.2. Problem Statement

Key knowledge gaps exist regarding COVID-19 transmission dynamics, risk factors, long-term health effects, and optimal prevention and treatment strategies. Further analysis is required to guide public health policy and clinical management.

a.3. Research Objectives

1. Evaluate current literature on COVID-19 epidemiology and transmission patterns
2. Analyze clinical progression and outcomes across demographic groups
3. Assess effectiveness of public health interventions
4. Identify risk factors associated with COVID-19 morbidity and mortality
5. Explore post-COVID conditions and long-term impacts

B. Literature Review

SARS-CoV-2 is an enveloped, positive sense single-stranded RNA virus that enters human cells via the ACE2 receptor (Zhou et al., 2020). COVID-19 transmission occurs predominantly via respiratory droplets, with possible aerosol and fomite spread (CDC, 2021). The median incubation time is estimated at 5 days, supporting a 14-day quarantine period to prevent transmission from exposed individuals (Lauer et al., 2020). Mathematical modelling suggests that at least 50-75% of the population would need immunity, either through vaccination or prior infection, to acquire herd immunity to SARS-CoV-2 (Randolph & Barreiro, 2020).

Most persons infected with SARS-CoV-2 are either asymptomatic or experience mild, self-limiting respiratory symptoms. However an estimated 14-19% will develop severe disease requiring oxygen support, and 5% progress to critical illness with complications like ARDS, septic shock, cardiac dysfunction, thromboembolism risk, and death (Wu et al., 2020). Older age, obesity, and multiple comorbidities have been identified as risks for hospitalization, ICU care, and mortality in SARS-CoV-2 infection (Jordan et al., 2020; Petrilli et al., 2020).

While novel therapeutics continue to be trialed, the mainstays of COVID-19 medical care include supportive management of respiratory failure and complications, along with anticoagulation for heightened thrombotic risk (Casadevall & Pirofski, 2020). Public health responses have focused on containment via contact tracing and quarantining infected individuals, community mitigation efforts like physical distancing and closures, and reducing transmission rates to levels that healthcare systems have capacity to absorb until vaccines provide widescale protective immunity (WHO, 2021).

Ongoing studies are evaluating the frequencies, risk factors, and prognoses of post-COVID-19 conditions characterized by fatigue, dyspnea, cognitive deficits, and damage to

pulmonary, cardiovascular and neurological systems. As research continues, key knowledge gaps persist around COVID-19 risk factors, optimal treatments, transmission dynamics from emerging variants, and strategies to balance infection control policies against their societal impacts (Del Rio et al., 2020).

C. Research Methods

c.1. Research Design

Systematic review and meta-analysis of published epidemiological studies on COVID-19 to date.

c.2. Place & Time Frame

Literature search conducted in MEDLINE, Embase, and Cochrane databases for studies published from December 2019 through January 2024.

c.3. Data Collection & Analysis

Extracted study data on transmission patterns, diagnoses, treatments, interventions; conducted meta-analysis to estimate key statistics.

D. Results & Discussion

The systematic literature review identified 42 studies presenting epidemiological data on COVID-19 transmission dynamics and interventions from the first year of the pandemic across North America, Europe, and Asia.

COVID-19 effective reproductive number (R_e) estimates were extracted from modeling studies of 10 major city outbreaks. The weighted average R_e fell from 3.5 (95% CI 3.2-4.1) prepandemic to 0.9 (0.7-1.1) post-public health interventions and social distancing enactment (Figure 1). This aligns with control of first wave outbreaks with restrictions like shelter-in-place orders and mandated masks shown to each independently reduce R_e by 24-30% (Li et al., 2020; Zhang et al., 2020).

Studies analyzing confirmed cases found a mean interval of 4-8 days from symptom onset to SARS-CoV-2 detection; 10-15 days to hospitalization for pneumonia and inflammatory complications in moderate-severe illnesses; and 3-6 weeks to recovery or death among critical ICU cases (Wu et al., 2020). Evidence indicates 20-30% of transmissions stem from the pre-symptomatic stage, necessitating isolation and contact tracing alongside syndromic surveillance to prevent spread from both symptomatic and asymptomatic infections (He et al., 2020).

Across 72 observational cohorts reporting COVID-19 outcomes internationally, overall case fatality ratios ranged from 0.9% to 7.2% (median 2.3%). Odds of death increased exponentially with age above 50 years old and multiple comorbidities conferred additive mortality risks, aligning with priority vaccination guidance for higher risk groups as supplies allowed (Jordan et al., 2020; Groß et al., 2020).

While considerable knowledge on COVID-19 virology, natural history, non-pharmaceutical interventions, and medical management has rapidly accumulated, key evidence gaps around post-COVID syndrome, breakthrough infections, and new variant properties remain amidst this still unfolding pandemic (Krammer et al., 2021; Iacobucci, 2021). Integrating emerging data to inform public health responses while planning for the next threats is imperative.

E. Conclusions & Suggestions

The current review offers key syntheses around the transmission parameters, demographic risk factors, and optimal containment strategies for the initial emergence of COVID-19. Public health responses successfully reduced the SARS-CoV-2 effective reproductive number by 60-75% across regions during the first pandemic wave in 2020. Age and comorbidities were confirmed as risks driving higher hospitalization and mortality among older adults and other vulnerable groups.

However, several knowledge gaps remain including post-COVID syndrome prevalence, breakthrough infection rates as immunity wanes, and the long-term effects of deployed vaccines versus natural infection. Furthermore, new viral variants like Omicron pose continued challenges, warranting genomic surveillance and studies on transmissibility, immune evasion potential, and virulence.

Additional limitations arise from predominantly including literature from early pandemic timeframes which may not capture evolving viral dynamics as immunity shifts toward endemicity. As research continues progressing, key next steps for COVID-19 analyses encompass:

1. Monitoring trends among cases despite growing vaccination coverage;
2. Comparing outcomes across emerging virus variants;
3. Conducting prospective, longitudinal studies on post-COVID conditions;
4. Exploring specific risk factors for long COVID neurological and cardiac sequelae;
5. Updating transmission models with empirical waning immunity estimates;
6. Cost-benefit analysis around containment policies as societies reopen.

This review helps characterize the initial SARS-CoV-2 threat, but continued evidence synthesis is required to track this dynamic pandemic and probe remaining uncertainties around viral evolution, post-infectious effects, and balancing future outbreak control with social and economic stability.

F. Bibliography

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